

Public Relations Strategies and Reputation Management of Nigeria's 10th National Assembly

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Abstract

The study addressed the persistent reputational challenges faced by Nigeria's 10th National Assembly, enhancing its public image amidst historical distrust. The specific objectives of this study were to: (i) identify the public relations strategies employed by the 10th National Assembly to manage its reputation; (ii) assess the effectiveness of these strategies in enhancing the Assembly's reputation; (iii) evaluate the reputation outcomes resulting from these strategies; and (iv) examine the challenges encountered in implementing reputation-oriented public relations efforts. Grounded in Excellence Theory and Institutional Theory, the research adopted a mixed-methods approach, collecting data through 326 fully completed questionnaire and 20 in-depth interviews with legislative aides, Public Relation officers, and journalists. Quantitative findings revealed the Public Relations strategies of the 10th National Assembly have achieved moderate success with mean scores ranging from 3.13-3.38, citizen awareness on legislative activities (Mean=3.36). Major structural challenges, such as limited funding (Mean=3.80), lack of personnel and resources (Mean=3.78), political meddling in communications (Mean=3.70) greatly restrict the effectiveness of PR efforts, the negative public perception on the National Assembly remains high (mean=3.70) while that of gradual improvement in perceived reputation is relatively low (mean=3.14). Qualitative insights highlighted initiatives like the National Assembly Open Week but noted inconsistencies in execution. Effectiveness was moderate, with stronger impacts on information dissemination (mean=3.36) than trust-building (mean=3.13). Reputation outcomes showed 44.8% agreement on improvements but 67.7% persistence of negative perceptions, driven by scandals. Challenges included resource shortages (mean=3.78), lack of coordination (mean=3.70). The study concluded that while PR strategies achieved modest gains, systemic barriers hindered transformative reputation enhancement, necessitating integrated approaches. Recommendation included strengthening of their communications strategies, encourage open and transparent communication, institutionalised ethical standard, establishing an autonomous PR unit, adopt empathetic crisis protocols and standardising intervention committees. The study established that the public relations strategies of Nigeria's 10th National Assembly achieved moderate success in enhancing its reputation but fell short of transformative impact due to systemic challenges and inconsistent implementation. Thus the findings offered a framework for strengthening legislative legitimacy in Nigeria's democratic context, aligning with global communication standards.

Keywords: Public Relations, Reputation Management, National Assembly, Excellence Theory, Institutional Theory

Introduction

Legislative institutions are fundamental to democratic governance, serving as platforms for lawmaking, representation, and oversight of the executive arm of government. In modern democracies, however, the effectiveness of legislative institutions is increasingly tied to public perception and trust. Reputation has become a strategic asset for public institutions in contemporary democracies. Legislative bodies, in particular, depend on public trust and legitimacy to effectively perform their constitutional responsibilities of lawmaking, representation, and oversight (Cutlip, Center & Broom, 2016). In recent years, increased media scrutiny and citizen participation, especially through digital platforms, have intensified the need for effective public relations practices within legislative institutions (Coombs, 2007).

In Nigeria, the National Assembly has consistently struggled with a damaged public image shaped by allegations of corruption, excessive remuneration, legislative inefficiency, and perceived elitism (Eze, 2022). Media reports and social media discourse often frame the legislature negatively, reinforcing public skepticism and distrust.

The rise of digital technologies has transformed the dynamics of public engagement in Nigeria. With over 100 million internet users by 2023 (NBS, 2023), social media platforms like Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook have become critical arenas for political discourse. These platforms empower citizens to demand transparency and accountability but also expose the National Assembly to rapid criticism and misinformation (Obasi & Eboh, 2021).

The inauguration of Nigeria's 10th National Assembly in June 2023 came with renewed public expectations for transparency, accountability, and responsiveness. In response, the Assembly has adopted various public relations strategies aimed at improving information dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and public understanding of legislative activities. Despite these efforts, public skepticism persists, raising questions about the effectiveness of these communication strategies.

Against this backdrop, this study examines the public relations strategies adopted by Nigeria's 10th National Assembly and assesses their effectiveness in managing institutional reputation in a challenging socio-political environment.

Statement of Problem

Public trust in democratic institutions is foundational to effective governance, yet legislative bodies worldwide grapple with reputational challenges that undermine their legitimacy. In Nigeria, a fragile democracy with a history of institutional distrust, the National Assembly faces persistent public skepticism due to allegations of corruption, lack of transparency, and perceived disconnection from constituents (Eze, 2022). These issues erode the Assembly's credibility, hindering its ability to fulfill its constitutional mandates of lawmaking, oversight, and representation. As public scrutiny intensifies, driven by digital media and an increasingly vocal civil society, effective reputation management becomes critical to restore confidence and strengthen democratic engagement. The absence of strategic communication practices exacerbates these challenges, leaving the legislature vulnerable to negative media framing and public backlash. Although the 10th National Assembly has adopted various communication initiatives aimed at improving transparency and public engagement, these efforts appear insufficient to reverse entrenched skepticism. Furthermore, challenges such as political interference, limited funding, lack of professional autonomy for public relations units, and inconsistent messaging continue to undermine strategic communication efforts (Grunig & Hunt, 1984).

The implications of this reputational crisis are profound. A legislature perceived as untrustworthy struggles to mobilise public support for policies, weakens its oversight functions, and undermines Nigeria's democratic resilience (Tuitjer & Dirksmeier, 2021). In a digital era where social media amplifies criticism, the absence of proactive, transparent, and dialogic communication strategies limits the Assembly's ability to counter negative narratives and engage citizens effectively. This study addresses this gap by examining the reputation management strategies of the 10th National Assembly, assessing their alignment with global PR best practices, and identifying barriers to their success. It is on this premise that this study seeks to investigate how these strategies shape public trust and enhance the Assembly's legitimacy in Nigeria's evolving democratic landscape.

Objectives of the Study

- i. To identify the Public Relations strategies employed by the 10th Nigerian National Assemblies to manage their reputation.
- ii. To assess the effectiveness of these Public Relations strategies in enhancing the reputation of the National Assembly.
- iii. To evaluate the reputation outcomes resulting from the National Assembly's Public Relations strategies.
- iv. To examine the challenges faced in implementing reputation-oriented Public Relations strategies within the National Assembly.

Research Questions

- i. What Public Relations strategies have been employed by the 10th Nigerian National Assemblies to manage their reputation?
- ii. How effective have these Public Relations strategies been in enhancing the reputation of the National Assembly?
- iii. What reputation outcomes have resulted from the Public Relations efforts of the 10th Nigerian National Assemblies?
- iv. What challenges are encountered in implementing reputation-focused Public Relations strategies within the National Assembly?

Conceptual Framework

Examining the PR Strategies Employed by the 10th National Assembly

Public relations has become an essential tool for the 10th Nigerian National Assembly as it seeks to improve its public image and rebuild citizens' trust in a climate of longstanding skepticism toward government institutions. Since its inauguration in 2023, the Assembly has increasingly recognized that effective communication is central to transparency, legitimacy, and democratic governance (Ojo, 2021).

One of the major strategies employed is structured media relations, including press briefings, press releases, and facilitated media coverage of plenary sessions. These efforts are designed not only to inform the public but also to manage narratives surrounding legislative decisions and activities. Effective media engagement, according to Ojo (2021), is critical for countering negative stereotypes about lawmakers' integrity and performance. In addition, the Assembly has embraced digital and social media platforms such as X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, and Instagram to communicate directly with citizens. This shift reflects a broader move toward real-time, participatory communication in governance (Eze, 2019).

However, the effectiveness of social media engagement remains uneven. While some legislators maintain consistent online presence, others engage only during elections or crises, resulting in fragmented messaging and limited long-term impact (Nwosu, 2021). To complement online engagement, the Assembly has intensified community outreach

programmes, including town hall meetings, constituency briefings, and civic education initiatives. These face-to-face interactions help project accessibility and responsiveness, which are key elements of positive public perception (Ajayi, 2022). Nonetheless, logistical and financial constraints, as well as the concentration of activities in urban areas, often limit their reach (Garba, 2019).

The Assembly has also pursued stakeholder engagement with civil society organizations, media professionals, and advocacy groups to promote transparency and cooperation. Yet, these efforts are largely ad hoc and lack a formal framework, reducing their strategic value (Nwosu, 2021). Transparency initiatives such as live broadcasting of plenary sessions have improved public understanding of legislative processes, though their impact on trust remains gradual (Ibrahim & Salihu, 2023).

Despite investments in communication training and the use of traditional media like radio and local-language broadcasts to reach rural populations (Udo, 2022), challenges persist. Political interference, weak crisis communication, inconsistent messaging, and deep-rooted public distrust continue to undermine reputation management efforts (Onah J, 2020; Olorunfemi, 2023). Overall, while the 10th National Assembly employs a diverse range of public relations strategies, sustainable reputation improvement will depend on institutionalizing a unified, professional, and transparent communication framework supported by ethical conduct and consistent public engagement.

Evaluating the Reputation Outcomes of Public Relations Strategies Adopted by the Nigerian National Assembly

Reputation remains a crucial yet fragile asset for the Nigerian National Assembly, as public trust and institutional legitimacy are essential for effective democratic governance. An assessment of the 10th National Assembly's public relations strategies shows that while increased communication has improved visibility and awareness, reputation outcomes remain uneven and often contradictory.

Greater transparency through live broadcasts of plenary sessions and regular digital updates has given citizens more access to legislative processes. This openness has helped improve public awareness and foster a sense of inclusion, particularly among politically engaged citizens (Ibrahim & Salihu, 2023). However, increased visibility has not always translated into positive perception. When legislative actions are viewed as controversial or unproductive, transparency has sometimes amplified public criticism rather than approval (Olorunfemi, 2023).

Social media engagement has further exposed lawmakers to public scrutiny. Although digital platforms allow direct interaction with citizens, their impact on reputation is limited by performative communication and inconsistent messaging. Many lawmakers use social media primarily for self-promotion rather than genuine dialogue, which often deepens public cynicism, especially among younger and digitally literate audiences (Eze, 2019; Adebayo, 2024).

Crisis communication remains a major weakness. Delayed or poorly coordinated responses to controversies such as budget disputes have allowed speculation and media narratives to dominate public discourse, eroding institutional credibility (Onah J, 2020). At the same time, community outreach initiatives, including town hall meetings and constituency engagements, have yielded localized trust gains. These face-to-face interactions strengthen representative credibility but are unevenly implemented, limiting broader institutional reputation benefits (Ajayi, 2022).

Another challenge lies in the disconnect between individual and collective reputation. While some legislators enjoy improved personal images, the overall perception of the Assembly remains negative due to the absence of a unified institutional communication strategy (Garba, 2019). Media framing further complicates reputation outcomes, as sensational or politically driven coverage often overshadows genuine legislative achievements (Ojo, 2021).

Despite these challenges, stakeholder partnerships with civil society groups and the use of performance data have offered modest reputational gains by promoting accountability and transparency (Ibrahim & Salihu, 2023). However, historical distrust and persistent ethical concerns continue to shape public perception. As Nwosu (2021) notes, reputation rebuilding requires consistent ethical behavior, not communication alone.

The reputation outcomes of the 10th National Assembly's PR efforts are mixed. While transparency and engagement have created short-term goodwill in some contexts, long-term trust remains fragile. Sustainable reputation management will depend on ethical legislative performance, coordinated communication, and continuous public feedback mechanisms.

Challenges in Implementing PR Strategies within the National Assembly

Implementing effective public relations strategies within the Nigerian National Assembly remains a complex task shaped by structural, political, and institutional challenges. One of the most pressing obstacles is inadequate funding. Limited budgetary allocation for communication activities has constrained the Assembly's ability to design and sustain comprehensive PR campaigns. As a result, communication efforts rely heavily on traditional tools such as press releases and media briefings, while investment in modern digital engagement remains minimal (Garba, 2019).

Budget limitations also affect the adoption of contemporary PR technologies. Unlike legislatures in more developed democracies that leverage data analytics and real-time digital platforms, the Nigerian National Assembly struggles to modernize its communication infrastructure, weakening its ability to connect effectively with citizens, especially younger and digitally active populations (Garba, 2019).

Political dynamics further complicate PR implementation. The Assembly's multiparty composition often results in conflicting priorities and fragmented messaging. Individual legislators frequently prioritize personal or party interests over institutional reputation, leading to inconsistent communication and weakened public trust (Bello, 2021). Leadership instability compounds this challenge, as frequent changes in Assembly leadership disrupt communication continuity and create shifting PR priorities, reinforcing perceptions of poor transparency and accountability (Okocha, 2020).

Another significant challenge is the lack of professional public relations expertise. Many officials responsible for communication lack formal training in media relations, crisis communication, and digital engagement. This skills gap results in reactive and poorly coordinated PR responses, particularly during controversies, limiting the Assembly's capacity to manage public perception effectively (Bello, 2021).

Media bias also undermines PR efforts. Legislative activities are often framed through narratives of corruption and inefficiency, overshadowing institutional achievements and reinforcing negative public perceptions. Such framing, driven by political interests and sensationalism, reduces the impact of official communication initiatives (Graber, 2019).

While social media offers opportunities for direct engagement, it has also exposed the Assembly to intense public criticism. Inconsistent online presence and crisis-driven engagement have allowed negative sentiments to dominate digital conversations, further damaging institutional reputation (Ajayi, 2022). Infrastructure challenges, particularly poor internet access in rural areas, exacerbate these issues by limiting the reach of digital PR efforts and deepening the urban–rural communication gap (Garba, 2019).

Ultimately, the effectiveness of PR strategies is undermined by persistent transparency and accountability concerns. Without addressing allegations of corruption and inefficiency, communication efforts alone cannot rebuild trust. Overcoming these challenges will require sustained investment in professional PR capacity, stable leadership, improved funding, and genuine institutional transparency.

Review of Empirical Studies

Adesina (2020), in *Legislative Crisis Communication in Nigeria: A Case Study of the 2016 Budget Padding Scandal*, explored the Nigerian National Assembly's PR response to a major credibility crisis. Using a case study methodology and discourse analysis, the study found that the Assembly's communication was defensive, vague, and reactionary. It concluded that the absence of a pre-crisis communication plan worsened reputational damage and recommended a more transparent, anticipatory communication model.

Okocha (2020), in *Legislative Leadership Transitions and Institutional PR in Nigeria*, studied how changes in Senate and House leadership impacted PR strategy continuity. Using qualitative interviews with Assembly media personnel, the study found that with each leadership change, new communication styles and agendas emerged, disrupting strategic messaging. Okocha recommended a centralised communication framework independent of leadership cycles.

Nwosu (2021), in *Community Outreach and Legislative Trust in Nigeria*, aimed to assess the effectiveness of the National Assembly's grassroots engagement strategies. Using surveys and focus groups across constituencies, the study found that town hall meetings and constituency dialogues improved public trust but were sporadic and uncoordinated. The research concluded that long-term trust required structured, inclusive, and regular engagement mechanisms.

This study aligns with the current research in evaluating outreach as a PR tool, but it lacks consideration of how digital platforms could extend and complement physical engagement. The current study bridges this gap by assessing the integration of digital outreach in the 10th Assembly and its resulting influence on reputation. It examines whether hybrid communication strategies foster more consistent engagement and improved credibility.

Bello (2021), in *Political Interference and Strategic Communication in the Nigerian Legislature*, used interviews with 15 communication officers and legislators to examine how political manipulation influenced PR outcomes. The study found that communications often reflected partisan agendas rather than institutional perspectives, thereby undermining public trust. Bello concluded that unless PR operations are depoliticised, strategic reputation management would remain unattainable.

Young (2021), in the study *Consistent PR and Public Confidence in the Australian Parliament*, employed longitudinal survey analysis and in-depth interviews with communication directors. The study found that consistent, non-partisan communication improved public trust, particularly when it involved regular updates, accessible messaging, and clear institutional voice. Young recommended that parliaments build communication infrastructure independent of political cycles to maintain reputation continuity. The current study aligns with Young's

emphasis on consistency but investigates whether Nigeria's 10th Assembly achieved this under conditions of high political turnover and media suspicion. Unlike the Australian context of political stability, the Nigerian setting poses structural and perceptual barriers, which this study assesses. It fills the gap by evaluating if institutional PR can survive leadership transitions in fragile democracies.

Ajayi (2022), in *Digital Media Engagement in Nigeria's Legislature: An Opportunity or Liability?* used platform analytics and legislative staff interviews to explore how digital communication tools were being utilised. Findings revealed that most social media use was ad hoc and surged during crises or political campaigns. The study recommended adopting long-term digital PR plans with clearly defined engagement metrics. Ajayi's findings underscore challenges that the current study interrogates more deeply. It assesses whether the 10th Assembly's digital engagement moved from reactive to strategic and whether these efforts improved public sentiment. The study's value lies in converting Ajayi's diagnosis into an outcome-based inquiry on reputation and trust.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Excellence Theory and Institutional Theory to explain how public relations practices influence reputation management within the Nigerian National Assembly. These theories are particularly relevant because they emphasize the role of communication in building trust, legitimacy, and institutional stability in democratic settings. Together, they provide a strong lens for understanding both the strategic and structural dimensions of public relations within legislative institutions.

Excellence Theory, developed by Grunig and Hunt (1984) and later expanded by Grunig (2008), posits that organizations achieve effective public relations when communication is strategic, ethical, and based on two-way symmetrical interaction. Rather than merely disseminating information, organizations are expected to engage their publics in dialogue, listen to feedback, and adjust policies accordingly. For a democratic institution like the National Assembly, this approach highlights the importance of engaging citizens as partners in governance rather than passive recipients of information.

Applied to the Nigerian National Assembly, Excellence Theory suggests that reputation can be strengthened when communication flows both ways, allowing lawmakers to explain legislative actions while also listening to public concerns. When citizens feel heard and included, trust and credibility are more likely to develop (Grunig, 2008). However, the theory also implies that one-way communication, propaganda, or reactive crisis messaging can weaken institutional reputation and deepen public distrust.

Institutional Theory complements this perspective by focusing on how organizations seek legitimacy by aligning their structures and practices with societal expectations (Scott, 2004). According to the theory, public institutions survive and gain acceptance not only through performance but also by conforming to norms such as transparency, accountability, and ethical conduct. For the National Assembly, public relations activities are therefore not just communication tools but signals of conformity to democratic values.

From an institutional standpoint, the communication strategies adopted by the 10th National Assembly such as broadcasting plenary sessions, engaging civil society groups, and publishing legislative performance data can be seen as efforts to maintain legitimacy in the eyes of the public (Suchman, 1995). When these actions align with public expectations, they reinforce institutional confidence; when they do not, reputational damage occurs regardless of communication intensity.

Institutional Theory also helps explain why PR efforts may fail despite increased visibility. Historical mistrust, political interference, and media skepticism shape how citizens interpret legislative communication. As Scott (2004) argues, legitimacy is socially constructed over time, meaning that reputation cannot be rebuilt through communication alone without consistent ethical behavior and institutional reform.

Together, Excellence Theory and Institutional Theory provide a comprehensive framework for this study. While Excellence Theory explains how communication should be conducted to foster mutual understanding, Institutional Theory explains why public relations must align with societal norms to achieve legitimacy. By integrating both theories, this study offers a balanced understanding of how strategic communication and institutional behavior jointly influence the reputation management efforts of Nigeria's 10th National Assembly.

Methodology

The study employed a mixed-methods research design, integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches to explore the reputation management strategies of Nigeria's 10th National Assembly. The quantitative strand facilitated the collection of measurable data on the types, frequency, and perceived effectiveness of PR strategies, while the qualitative strand provided in-depth insights into institutional practices, stakeholder perceptions, and contextual challenges. This design was justified by the need to capture both statistical trends and nuanced perspectives, ensuring a holistic understanding of how PR strategies shaped the Assembly's reputation (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).

The population comprised individuals directly or indirectly involved in the development, implementation, monitoring, or perception of the 10th National Assembly's PR strategies. This included 469 Senior Legislative Aides (SLAs), with one aide per lawmaker (109 Senators and 360 House of Representatives members), 1,198 Public Relations Officers (453 in the Senate and 745 in the House of Representatives), 2 Committee Clerks (one each from the Senate and House), and 80 accredited journalists covering the National Assembly (National Assembly Service Commission, 2023). The total population was 1,749 individuals, spanning legislative staff, media professionals, and communication personnel based in Abuja, Nigeria's political hub.

For the quantitative component, the sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula for finite populations:

$$n = N / (1 + N \times e^2)$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- N = population size
- e = margin of error (0.05 for 95% confidence level)

Given a combined population of institutional stakeholders (SLAs + Staffs + Journalists) as $N = 1,749$, the calculation will be:

$$n = 1,749 / (1 + 1,749 \times 0.0025)$$

$$n = 1,749 / (1 + 4.3725)$$

$$n = 1,749 / 5.3725 \approx 325.5$$

Thus, a sample of 326 respondents was selected. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed: purposive sampling identified legislators and staff in communication-related roles, stratified random sampling ensured balance across departments (Senate, House) and roles (SLAs, PR officers, journalists), and systematic random sampling selected digitally active

public members following National Assembly social media handles.

For the qualitative component, 20 participants were selected for in-depth interviews, comprising 5 senior PR officers, 5 legislators (PR/Committee leads), 5 senior media correspondents, and 5 civic leaders or social commentators. Purposive and snowball sampling were used to recruit knowledgeable informants, with snowball sampling allowing participants to recommend other relevant stakeholders. This sample size was justified by data saturation principles, ensuring comprehensive insights without redundancy (Guest et al., 2006). The approach ensured diverse perspectives but risked bias from purposive selection, potentially limiting generalizability.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Awareness and Use of PR Strategies

Item	Strongly Disagree f (%)	Disagree f (%)	Neutral f (%)	Agree f (%)	Strongly Agree f (%)	Mean	SD
The 10th National Assembly uses social media effectively to engage the public.	32 (9.8)	45 (13.8)	60 (18.4)	120 (36.8)	69 (21.2)	3.46	1.24
Press conferences and media briefings are regularly organised by the Assembly.	25 (7.7)	50 (15.3)	55 (16.9)	130 (39.9)	66 (20.2)	3.50	1.19
Legislators participate in community outreach programmes to connect with citizens.	40 (12.3)	55 (16.9)	70 (21.5)	110 (33.7)	51 (15.6)	3.24	1.25
The Assembly maintains an active and updated website or digital platform.	28 (8.6)	48 (14.7)	62 (19.0)	125 (38.3)	63 (19.3)	3.45	1.20

Legislative debates and sessions are made publicly accessible to promote transparency.	35 (10.7)	52 (16.0)	65 (19.9)	115 (35.3)	59 (18.1)	3.34	1.25
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Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 1 depicts awareness and use of PR strategies across items, with means ranging from 3.24 to 3.50, indicating moderate positive perceptions overall (above neutral threshold of 3). Higher agreement on media briefings (mean=3.50, SD=1.19) suggests stronger recognition of formal channels, while lower scores for outreach (mean=3.24, SD=1.25) highlight potential gaps in grassroots implementation. The consistent SD around 1.2-1.25 reflects moderate variability, implying some consensus but room for targeted improvements in digital and community engagement to boost perceived utilisation.

Table 2: Effectiveness of PR Strategies

Item	Strongly Disagree f (%)	Disagree f (%)	Neutral f (%)	Agree f (%)	Strongly Agree f (%)	Mean	SD
PR strategies have improved the public image of the National Assembly.	38 (11.7)	60 (18.4)	70 (21.5)	105 (32.2)	53 (16.3)	3.23	1.25
Citizens are better informed about legislative activities due to PR efforts.	30 (9.2)	55 (16.9)	65 (19.9)	120 (36.8)	56 (17.2)	3.36	1.21
Social media has made legislators more accountable.	42 (12.9)	58 (17.8)	68 (20.9)	110 (33.7)	48 (14.7)	3.20	1.26
Community engagement has increased public trust in the Assembly.	45 (13.8)	62 (19.0)	72 (22.1)	100 (30.7)	47 (14.4)	3.13	1.27
Media relations have been professionally handled by PR officers.	33 (10.1)	50 (15.3)	60 (18.4)	125 (38.3)	58 (17.8)	3.38	1.23

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 2 shows effectiveness perceptions, with means from 3.13 to 3.38, signaling mild agreement on informational impacts (e.g., citizen awareness, mean=3.36, SD=1.21) but weaker on trust-building (community engagement, mean=3.13, SD=1.27). The SD values (1.21-1.27) indicate similar dispersion, suggesting polarized views that could stem from inconsistent strategy execution, with implications for prioritizing professional media handling to elevate overall efficacy.

Table 3: Challenges in Implementation

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean	SD
Political interference affects the consistency of PR messages.	20 (6.1)	35 (10.7)	50 (15.3)	140 (42.9)	81 (24.8)	3.70	1.14
PR units in the National Assembly lack adequate resources and staffing.	18 (5.5)	30 (9.2)	45 (13.8)	145 (44.5)	88 (27.0)	3.78	1.11
Media bias undermines the Assembly's image regardless of its PR efforts.	25 (7.7)	40 (12.3)	55 (16.9)	135 (41.4)	71 (21.8)	3.57	1.18
There is a lack of coordination among communication departments.	22 (6.7)	38 (11.7)	52 (16.0)	138 (42.3)	76 (23.3)	3.64	1.16
Outreach programmes are limited due to funding constraints.	15 (4.6)	28 (8.6)	48 (14.7)	150 (46.0)	85 (26.1)	3.80	1.06

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 3 highlights implementation challenges, with elevated means (3.57-3.80) confirming strong agreement on barriers like funding (mean=3.80, SD=1.06) and resources (mean=3.78, SD=1.11). Lower SD (around 1.1) indicates greater consensus here than in other sections, implying widespread acknowledgment of systemic issues that could undermine PR efforts, with strategic resource allocation as a key implication for mitigation.

Table 4. Reputation Outcomes

Item	Strongly Disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)	Mean	SD
The Assembly's reputation has improved under the 10th legislature.	40 (12.3)	65 (19.9)	75 (23.0)	100 (30.7)	46 (14.1)	3.14	1.24
Citizens are more willing to engage with legislators than before.	35 (10.7)	60 (18.4)	70 (21.5)	110 (33.7)	51 (15.6)	3.25	1.23

Negative public perception still persists despite PR efforts.	20 (6.1)	35 (10.7)	50 (15.3)	140 (42.9)	81 (24.8)	3.70	1.14
The Assembly is now seen as more transparent and accountable.	38 (11.7)	55 (16.9)	68 (20.9)	105 (32.2)	60 (18.4)	3.29	1.27
There is improved media coverage of legislative achievements.	42 (12.9)	58 (17.8)	65 (19.9)	102 (31.3)	59 (18.1)	3.24	1.30

Source: Field Survey 2025

Table 4 illustrates reputation outcomes, with means varying from 3.14 (reputation improvement) to 3.70 (persistent negatives), reflecting ambivalent results where challenges outweigh gains (SD=1.14-1.30). High agreement on lingering perceptions (mean=3.70) suggests PR limitations, implying the need for evidence-based interventions to shift means upward and reduce variability for sustained legitimacy.

Qualitative Data Presentation

Use of PR Strategies

Respondents highlighted a mix of traditional and digital strategies employed by the 10th National Assembly, including social media, press briefings, community outreach, and events like the National Assembly Open Week. R1 (Legislative Aides) emphasized, "that House of Representatives hosted the second edition of the National Assembly Open Week, a three-day programme which was broadcasted live... The Open Week presented a specific PR strategies the 10th National Assembly employed to manage its public image." Similarly, R4 (Legislative Aides) noted dynamic programs for citizen engagement, stating, "The 10th National Assembly is reasserting its commitment to citizen engagement and participatory democracy through dynamic programs." Platforms mentioned include NassTv, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter (X), and the website nass.gov.ng, with R5 (PR Officer) adding, "Using National Assembly Magazine, which document activities, highlights National Assembly stories and News updates." However, evolution from previous assemblies was mixed; R2 (Assistant Chief Official Reporter) critiqued, "The movement is very poor they were more conciliatory, prioritizing stability and speedy passage of executive bills for their personal gain." R8 (SLA) praised intervention committees as unique, saying, "Creation of intervention committees: they always brought a good solution to national issues like Labour strike, Asuu." Analysis reveals a shift toward digital tools for real-time engagement, but inconsistencies in implementation suggest reactive rather than proactive approaches. This implies that while strategies aim to foster transparency, fragmented execution limits their reach, particularly in addressing historical distrust, necessitating more coordinated efforts to align with global best practices.

Effectiveness of Strategies

Perceptions of effectiveness varied, with some praising impacts on public perception and others noting limitations. R1 viewed strategies as "practically realistic, easy to relate and supportive

listeners," citing Open Week's influence: "The event also include an interactive session... captures the House's legislative achievements." R3 (Journalist) acknowledged media's role, "Allowing media correspondence to convey, disseminate National Assembly Chamber debate... serves as a story telling tool to regain trust." Metrics for success included public feedback and media coverage, as R4 stated, "The platforms have informed, empower and protected the rights of the people... connected with over 7000 citizens especially youth." However, R2 was critical: "Zero improvement... that more people say the same," pointing to low performance. R6 (PRO) added, "There is nothing Special and remarkable... the PR unit have no muscles to change the narrative." R7 (PRO) saw it as a "continuous process not by magic." Analysis indicates partial effectiveness in informational dissemination (e.g., via digital platforms), but weaker in trust-building due to perceived corruption and inconsistencies. Implications suggest that while events like Open Week amplify positive narratives, overall effectiveness is undermined by public skepticism, requiring data-driven metrics like engagement analytics to refine strategies and enhance reputational outcomes.

Challenges in Implementation

Key challenges included resource shortages, coordination issues and political interference. R2 highlighted corruption: "They are as wild fire of corruption... no sign of hope." R6 noted, "Political corruption as a serious challenge... corrupt politicians could utilize illicitly obtained resources for their electoral campaigns." R7 emphasized leadership incompetence: "The major problem is who lead... an incompetent person will be posted to lead a department that he can't manage." Resource lacks were common, with R5 stating, "There are problems in the implementation," and R8 adding, "PR unit finance down, a proper budget will do it." Media bias and public backlash were noted by R3: "There are plenty campaigns contract... but for political reasons they always say NO." R9 (CPSA) suggested training gaps: "High level of training is required for staffs... particularly in area of communication." Analysis shows systemic barriers like interference erode message credibility, while under-resourcing hampers modern tools. Implications point to the need for autonomy in PR units and ethical reforms, as persistent challenges perpetuate negative perceptions, risking further erosion of legitimacy in a digital scrutiny era.

Outcomes and Public Perception

Outcomes were perceived as mixed, with some improvements in engagement but persistent distrust. R1 observed positive reactions: "It's a good recommendations that keeps coming... they must be commended." R4 noted, "There is a sign on peoples face during National Assembly Open Week." However, R2 saw "The image of 10th Assembly is very rough around edges... no improvement." R3 described public reaction as "actually negative," and R5 said, "Public reaction to current Assembly's PR efforts is bad." R6 echoed, "The observable public reaction is not good same with the national Assembly image." Compared to past assemblies, R4 praised, "Yes for the first term the 10th National Assembly introduced a program (OPEN WEEK)... change all the wrong narratives." But R2 countered, "On these they are on the same level." Analysis reveals incremental gains in transparency but enduring negative perceptions due to scandals. Implications underscore that without addressing root causes like corruption, PR efforts yield limited outcomes, suggesting a need for measurable trust indicators to track progress and bolster democratic legitimacy.

Suggestions

Suggestions focused on training, engagement, and reforms. R9 recommended, "High level of training... to inform the public accurately, reduce misinformation." R10 (PRO) suggested,

"Large area councils security meetings, constituency visit... to boost public engagement." R11 (Journalist) advocated, "Facilitate a national discourse on how to curb election malpractices." R12 (SLA) proposed, "Constant meetings... to get closer to the people." R13 (PRO) called for, "Frequent, professional capacity building services on methods... Legislative Staff capacity shortages will be addressed." R14 (PRO) emphasized education: "Wide education and explanation to the public on the functions... of our legislatives." R15 (PRO) urged, "More assertive in performing their constitutional functions." R16 (PRO) suggested, "Provide an adequate and modern working equipment." R17 (PRO) proposed incentives: "Provision for imprest incentive and overtime allowance." R18 (Journalist) called for, "Decisive action... to overhaul and break the mould." R19 (PRO) addressed, "Poor communication strategy, weak coordination and political interference... must be address." R3 recommended amendments: "Need for amendment of the legislative Houses (Powers and Privileges)... to make more explicit the provisions." R6 suggested, "Foster constructive engagement... through transparent communication." R7 proposed, "Political interference must be avoid... the National Assembly Open week programme is a well come development." Analysis integrates these into a framework for proactive PR, emphasizing merit-based structures and digital enhancements. Implications highlight that implementing these could transform the Assembly's image from reactive to citizen-focused, fostering sustainable trust and aligning with theoretical models like Excellence Theory for mutual dialogue.

Discussion of Findings

The study reveals that Nigeria's 10th National Assembly employs a mix of public relations strategies aimed at improving transparency, engagement, and institutional reputation. These strategies include media relations, digital communication, community outreach, stakeholder engagement, and crisis management. Quantitative findings show moderate agreement on the deployment of these strategies, with mean scores ranging between 3.24 and 3.50, suggesting that while PR mechanisms are in place, their application is neither weak nor fully robust. Qualitative evidence, such as references to initiatives like the National Assembly Open Week and intervention committees, further illustrates deliberate efforts to foster openness and manage reputational risks.

The findings align broadly with Excellence Theory, which emphasizes two-way symmetrical communication and dialogue rather than one-way information dissemination (Grunig & Hunt, 1984). The Assembly's use of social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter has enabled real-time interaction with citizens, reflecting global best practices in democratic communication (Lilleker & Koc-Michalska, 2017). However, these efforts are undermined by inconsistencies, including irregular updates and reactive engagement, echoing Nwosu's (2021) critique of Nigerian legislative PR as largely episodic rather than strategic. Historical distrust rooted in Nigeria's military past further complicates public acceptance of these initiatives (Eze, 2022).

In assessing effectiveness, the study shows moderate success across several outcome indicators. Mean scores ranging from 3.13 to 3.38 indicate mild agreement that PR strategies have improved public image, information dissemination, and engagement. Media relations emerged as one of the more effective tools, with over half of respondents acknowledging professional handling of press interactions. This finding reinforces Excellence Theory's emphasis on ethical and accountable communication.

Digital communication also showed measurable impact, particularly in enhancing transparency and citizens' willingness to engage. Social media and the official National Assembly website were identified as key channels for real-time updates, supporting Ajayi's (2022) view that

digital platforms can bypass traditional media filters. However, qualitative responses highlighted fragmented digital identities and inconsistent posting, diverging from Eze's (2019) argument that sustained online presence is essential for trust-building. Institutional Theory explains this gap as "decoupling," where institutions symbolically adopt modern practices without fully embedding them operationally (Scott, 2004).

Community engagement, while valued, was the least effective strategy. Quantitative results showed the lowest mean score for its impact on trust, largely due to funding and logistical constraints that limit outreach to urban areas. This finding aligns with Garba's (2019) observation that resource limitations weaken grassroots communication in Nigeria and contrasts with evidence from mature democracies where consistent community engagement strengthens institutional trust (Davis, 2019).

Stakeholder engagement and crisis communication produced mixed outcomes. While ad hoc dialogues with civil society groups and intervention committees helped address specific issues, the lack of a structured engagement framework limited their long-term impact. This partially aligns with Excellence Theory's emphasis on ethical relationships but falls short of institutionalized best practices (Centre for Legislative Engagement, 2023). Crisis responses were sometimes effective but often defensive, diverging from Coombs' (2007) recommendation for proactive and empathetic crisis communication.

Overall, reputation outcomes were ambivalent. Although some respondents acknowledged improvements in transparency, engagement, and media coverage, persistent negative perceptions, media bias, and political interference continued to erode trust (Eze, 2019; Graber, 2019). Institutional Theory explains these mixed results through legitimacy pressures and historical skepticism, suggesting that communication alone cannot repair reputation without consistent ethical performance (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Scott, 2004).

The findings reveal that the implementation of reputation-oriented public relations strategies within the Nigerian National Assembly is constrained by multiple, interrelated challenges. Resource shortages emerged as a major barrier, with inadequate funding and staffing limiting strategic planning, training, and outreach activities (Nwosu, 2021; Grunig & Hunt, 1984). Political interference was also strongly evident, as partisan interests often override institutional communication goals, resulting in inconsistent messaging and weakened credibility (Bello, 2021). This aligns with Institutional Theory's explanation of coercive pressures that undermine organizational autonomy (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983).

Media bias further complicates reputation management, as negative framing of legislative activities tends to overshadow PR efforts, reinforcing public skepticism (Graber, 2019; Entman, 2007). In addition, poor coordination among communication units creates fragmented messaging, contrary to best practices in integrated communication (Nwosu, 2021). Training gaps and limited professionalization also reduce PR effectiveness (Bello, 2019). Overall, these challenges highlight the need for structural reforms, increased funding, and greater institutional autonomy to strengthen reputation management within the Assembly.

Conclusion

The study established that the public relations strategies of Nigeria's 10th National Assembly achieved moderate success in enhancing its reputation but fell short of transformative impact due to systemic challenges and inconsistent implementation. The significant contributions of social media and press conferences to public image and transparency have over the years proven to overcome many communication challenges, unfavourable opinion, and poor impression/image that limited trust-building and legitimacy.

These findings, grounded in Excellence and Institutional Theories, highlight the need for cohesive, proactive strategies to align with Nigeria's democratic aspirations and global communication standards.

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